

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME:** Constance**FIRST NAME:** Enongene-Kome**PROGRAM CODE:** DIPH**COURSE CODE:** ACA-401D**PERIOD NUMBER:** 6**INSTRUCTOR:** Dr. Gulma**Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software: Microsoft Word 2019 on Windows 10

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. Which of the following components of a dissertation or an academic paper should be single-spaced?
 - Dissertation chapters.
 - Sub-sections in the dissertation.
 - All of the above.
 - Bibliographies or reference lists.**¹

2. The following is an example of a qualitative data collection method.
 - Questionnaires.

¹ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for the Writers of Research Papers, Thesis, and Dissertations* (Chicago Style for Students and Researchers: University of Chicago Press Editorial Staff, 2018), 423.

- Focus group discussions.**²
- Cross-sectional studies.
- None of the above.
3. What is a set of structural conventional settings which guides the writing of dissertations or manuscripts?
- General format requirements.**³
- Basic rules.
- Guiding principles.
- Academic paper.
4. What is the conventional page margin to be used in a dissertation document?
- 5.5 x 8.5 inches.
- 8.5 x 14 inches.
- 8 $\frac{1}{2}$ x 11 inches.**⁴
- 8.27 x 11.69 inches
5. The front matter of a dissertation usually comprises the following elements except what?
- Table of contents.

² Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation* (Road Map from Beginning to End: Columbia University, 2019), 457.

³ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for the Writers of Research Papers, Thesis, and Dissertations*, 395.

⁴ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for the Writers of Research Papers, Thesis, and Dissertations*, 395.

- List of references.**⁵
- The dedication page.
- The abstract page.
6. What is the difference between pure research and applied research?
- Pure research addresses a conceptual problem that does not have any direct practical consequences while applied research addresses a practical problem that has practical consequences.**⁶
- Pure and applied research does not require resources.
- Pure and applied research is not applicable in the academic spaces.
- None of the above.
7. Interviews are used in a qualitative research methodology as?
- Case study.
- Ethnography.
- Qualitative data collection method.**⁷
- Phenomenology.
8. What is the en rule (-) used for?
- Shows periods of two or more complete years only.

⁵ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for the Writers of Research Papers, Thesis, and Dissertations*, 423.

⁶ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for the Writers of Research Papers, Thesis, and Dissertations*, 29.

⁷ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation*, 454.

- For parenthetical expressions only.
- Set parenthetical expressions, indicate ranges of numbers, and show periods of two more complete years.⁸**
- None of the above.

9. In presenting research findings tables are used to express which of the following?

- To emphasize specific values.⁹**
- To emphasize comparisons at a glance.
- To emphasize trends.
- All of the above.

10. Style guides are?

- Not vital in developing academic essays or dissertations.
- Means of documenting one's approach as a writer to certain elements of writing style that needs to be consistent.¹⁰**
- None of the above.
- All of the above.

⁸ WHO, *WHO Style Guide* (WHO Headquarters and WHO Regional Office for Europe, 2013), 34.

⁹ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for the Writers of Research Papers, Thesis, and Dissertations*, 87.

¹⁰ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA401D Coursepack* (Period 1: Euclid University, 2021), 24.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda Dale and Marie F. Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation. A Road Map from Beginning to End*: Columbia University, 2019.

Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. 3rd ed. Bangui: Euclid University, 2021.

Turabian, L. Kate. *A Manual for the Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. 9th ed. Revised by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, William T. FitzGerald, and the University of Chicago Press Editorial Staff. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018.

WHO. *WHO Style Guide*: WHO headquarters, and WHO Regional Office for Europe, 2013.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.